

**THE EFFECTS OF GLOBALIZATION PROCESSES
(1453-1869 / 1870-1914) ON THE OTTOMAN STATE
SPORTS INSTITUTION**

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Abstract:

The purpose of our work is to determine the effects of the first and second period globalization processes on the sports institutions of the Ottoman State. This aim is to be able to explain the tendency of the globalization which emerged as a continuation of each other in accordance with the spirit of the era of the Turkish sport institutions. Globalization is a very influential phenomenon on the changes of states, social and economic institutions. Globalization; can be regarded as a concept that deals with a wide variety of disciplines and markets, and establishes relationships that influence and interfere with these disciplines and markets. From this perspective, it is also a fact that the effects of countries on sports institutions are inevitable. In the study, a qualitative method called "descriptive field scanning", documentary or documentary study was followed. In this way, our research has been structured by the historical research method and the historical survey method with qualitative research in terms of content. Historical research methodology has been supported by archival scanning method based on reviewing, translating, reading and evaluating books, documents, files, official and private correspondence documents, foreign language information and documents. The sports schools of the Ottoman state's sports institutions were weakened by the loss of their importance by being negatively affected as the economic aims of the establishment causes with the change of trade routes in the first globalization process. In the second globalization process; despite the fact that the Ottoman state was in its recent times, it tried to adapt to the socio-economic changes brought about by Globalization. At the end of this effort, importance has been given to sports and sports

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institutions in education, social life. He transferred both the sports institutions and the sports workforce to the state of the Republic of Turkey, which is the continuation of the Ottoman state.

Keywords: globalization, Ottoman State, sports organizations, sports schools, sports corporation

1. Introduction

The aim of our work is to determine the effects of the globalization processes of the first and second period on the sports institutions of the Ottoman State. This aim is to be able to explain the tendency of the globalization which emerged as a continuation of each other in accordance with the spirit of the era of the Turkish sports institutions. Globalization is a very influential phenomenon on the changes of states, social and economic institutions. Globalization; can be regarded as a concept that deals with a wide variety of disciplines and markets, and establishes relationships that influence and interfere with these disciplines and markets. From this point of view, it is clear that it is also influential on the sports institutions of the countries.

In this study, a qualitative method called "descriptive field scanning", documentary or documentary study was followed (Karasar, 1976, Kaptan, 1983). This research is structured by the scanning method and historical research method used in historical studies together with qualitative research in terms of content. The historical research method is supported by archival scanning method based on the examination, translation, reading, and evaluation of books, documents, files, official and private correspondence documents, foreign language information and documents (Arıkan, 1995, Arlı, 2004).

Globalization has entered the literature for the first time, using McLuhan's "global village" concept for the new world order in his book "Gutenberg Galaxy" written in 1962. In his book, McLuhan described globalization, stating that at least a part of the world is becoming a "global village", especially through improvements in communication technologies. The second claim is that as a continuation of the first, the concept has been updated in the 1980's by distinguished American business schools such as Harvard, Stanford, and Colombia, especially by the support of American scholar Zbigniew Brzezinski, an expert of communism from Colombia University and some economists (Zigler, 2004). The third claim is that Anthony Giddens of the London School of Economics (Gökdere, 2001), who said that the term "globalization" was first introduced between the end of the 1980s and the beginning of 1990s. According to

Giddens, globalization is the intensification of social relations on the world scale (Giddens, 1990) in the context of events in a country having an influence on events in other places or influencing events outside the national boundaries. Pranab Bardhan, who approaches economics to the concept of globalization, (Zengingönül, 2005), the globalization in the "Social Justice in the Global Economy" forum organized by the International Labor Organization (ILO) in South Africa means that integration of the international economy is essential and that external trade and investment is to be accepted.

In terms of our field of work, this study will focus on the first and second periods of globalization and its effects.

2. First Globalization Period: 1453 Conquest of Istanbul to 1800's Years' End

After the conquest of Istanbul by the Ottoman State in 1453, which was accepted as the beginning of the first globalization period, the Western countries entered different quests. On the basis of these quests, overseas trips have begun to explore new places and trade. With the emergence of nation-states in this period, Western countries began to spread political, military and commercial influence over overseas countries, and colonialism became institutionalized in this period. With this first colonial movement, the gold and silver mine became precious, and the current of mercantilism, which advocated that the main riches of the states were in precious metals and that they were protective, started in this period. Sea expeditions and colonization policies have been transformed into imperialism in the process, and resources from the colonized lands have been moved to Europe to enrich and develop Europe. Enrichment has also been provided not only in economic life, but also in science, thought, culture and social life, and has also provided the basis for the industrial revolution after the emergence of industrialization activities (Elçin, 2012).

The effect of this period on the Ottoman sports institutions was as follows. It is understood that in the Ottoman Empire, the municipal services and sports institutions are based entirely on the foundations of the foundation, operation, and financing.

In fact, some of the researchers of the foundations argue that it would be more appropriate to consider the institution as a secular and social institution rather than a religious institution (Kuban 1968: 68). In the Ottoman period, the government did not have any financial contribution to the execution of the municipal services in the city and it contributed to the provision of such services. The needs of the municipal services were being carried out through voluntary organizations, without paying taxes. Foundations were set up to provide services such as roads, water, street lighting, park

and garden arrangements from services that modern municipalities are obliged to do and that they must do. As mentioned above, since no contribution has been received from the public, the services have not been distinguished while they are being delivered. In addition to the public duties we have mentioned above, the foundations have military service. Foundations serving fortress, fortification, navy, cannon, shipyard, longer household, artillery, foundry, swordfish foundations, foundation for helping those who are seen benefiting in naval and land warfare were being utilized for the purpose of purchasing and training horses the field service.

At the same time, as well as establishing sports squares, swimming, athletics, riding, arrows and javelin throwing, as well as welfare athletes, It reveals the importance of foundations in the defense of the Ottoman state and in the military field (Ateş 1988).

During the first globalization process, the Ottoman state conquered Istanbul and became an empire. During the establishment phase of the state, the sports schools had three important functions. The first one is to meet the sports needs of the people, the second one economic and the third one military purpose. The Ottoman state decision-makers were setting up sports schools in the rural areas where they would settle. Later on, settlement began around these sports schools and over time they were getting the city. Another purpose was to establish sports schools on the trade routes, thus securing the trade routes, also called the Silk Road. However, with the westerners discovering the sea route, the development of the Silk Road has stopped, and over time, the importance has decreased. This development has also reduced the importance of sports schools. This change in trade routes has also adversely affected both the cities on the old trade route and the development of sports schools.

3. Second Globalization Period: 1870 Industrial Revolution-1914 First World War

The beginning of the second period of globalization was realized by the Industrial Revolution which started in 1870. In this process, the transfer of colonialist policies and the resources of the colonial countries continued to the Western countries, enrichment and capital accumulation continued. The Industrial Revolution has created a liberal economic system in the late 19th Century, with the beginning of free trade theories. In this period when international trade barriers have not restricted capital and labor mobility, commodity trade has reached important dimensions. Due to the absence of obstacles to labor mobility, inexpensive labor to developed countries in order to find better jobs has reduced input costs in production, which in turn has led to more capital accumulation and more investment opportunities. Innovations such as steam vessels,

railroads, telegraphs, and telephones that emerged during this period have increased communication between countries, reduced distances and allowed the workforce to capitalize on production and to quickly shift production. The globalization movement that started to develop after the Industrial Revolution lost its momentum in 1914 when the First World War broke out (Elçin, 2012).

The Turkish people who were exhausted in the series of long wars were left uneducated and untrained (Fisek, 1980). Thus, the young generation of the Ottoman state, II, despite being able to defend their homeland and their homeland in the era of globalization, they were caught up in imprudence and powerlessness.

The practices of the Ottoman state lawmakers led the Turks to a full decadent process of decline while the world was experiencing different developments. Especially the industrial revolution, which began to rise from the mid-18th century, strengthened the "nation state" phenomenon, which began to organize small, scattered and unconnected local markets around a single national market. The glorification of the nation's honor, the provision of national integrity, and the protection of the nation's boundaries have also brought along. Gymnastics and sports activities gained military and political content in a very intense way, adding to all these changing circumstances of wars (Ateş, 2012).

The first examples came from the French, who made the leading role of rising nationalism and nationalism. As Selim Sir Tarcan stated,

"On the eve of the French Revolution, in the part of the school which was taken out by the French, the condition of making gymnastics, various power sports, and military drills according to the ages of the students were introduced and the authority of supervision was left to the soldiers."

In this context, physical activities paralleling French politics will start to follow a path as Andre Chenier said in a small part of his speech:

"... a captive nation does not need these training. They must remain weaker than they are obliged to serve. A generation ruled by the Republic should be strong. Thus, the first steps were taken to establish the citizens' army through education. After Napoleon Bonaparte had been on the throne of the empire, he obliged practicing gymnastics and military training in private schools besides the public schools in the direction of these ideas. The French young people, who were physically prepared for war, began to be driven into battlefields for European invasion in the direction of Napoleon's ideals."

(Selim Sirri, 1928)

In Britain, the democratic and libertarian environment that has lived led to the birth of many sports. Educator Thomas Arnold (1795-1842) convinced these sports that he could be used in the education of British youth. Based on sportive bases, this training movement, which we have initiated in Rugby College, proved that body education can develop in a balanced and formative manner (Alpman, 1972).

However, especially since the second half of the nineteenth century, the strengthening of the idea of imperialism and colonialism has abandoned the Arnold understanding.

In the beginning, the young people were training as Arnold wanted who were able to control the clean, modest, orderly, tone of voice and physical strength, were later raised to take on musculoskeletal and rigid diversity is claimed that Darwin's theory of evolution, which began to hold at the end of the nineteenth century, supported a dark sport in masculinity ideals, a support for the spread of imperialist invasions, the need to defend new or existing colonies (Marschik, 2001) the dominant countries, England and Germany, have given their sporting institutions more power than other countries before World War I. Germany was preparing for it with youth organizations and gymnastics clubs, while England was waiting for the sport clubs and scouting that they made into an industry.

The traditional Ottoman worldview, based on Islam and Turkish tradition, has undergone a great transformation since the 19th century. This transformation would bring about significant changes in both individual and community life. The movements of humanism, positivism, and materialism coming from Europe to Turkey were basically opposite to traditional Turkish Islamic understanding. Therefore, the new physical education brought by these movements coincided with the basic education which received the religion and doctrine. While these currents emerging in Europe attaches extreme importance to the human body, traditional understanding does not place the human body in the exact center. The purpose of preserving your body, and therefore of physical education, was purely worldly. The Ottoman society, built on Islamic understanding, integrated forces and bodies with jihad and Gaza intellectuals. The purpose of keeping the body strong in such an infrastructure was not only worldly but also ethereally at the same time It was necessary to keep the body strong either to be able to make jihad in the way of religion or to perform the worship properly. (Öymen, 1982).

However, this understanding over time has left the place to those who think and live like Europeans. If the Tanzimat period is viewed only as political, military and administrative reforms, this period is not sufficiently understood. The Tanzimat was also a cultural revolution for civic life in a limited sense (Zürcher, 1996). Non-Muslims

enriched by European merchants and their commercial connections established a new lifestyle and standard of living for the Ottoman cities. While the neighborhoods in which they lived were becoming more and more developed and alive, the Muslim neighborhoods remained calm and dignified (Baykara, 2007). In the neighborhoods and districts where they lived, there were clubs and various entertainment places, and after a while, Muslim statesmen and rich people started to come and go. As a result of this relationship, Europe's lifestyle was beginning to spread and adopt among Muslims. Mustafa Reşit Pasha, Ali Pasha, and Fuat Pasha, who are the most important actors of the Tanzimat period, are the result of the struggle and the daily culture of the western part of the Ottoman Empire became more effective than ever before. Clothing, home furnishings, style of houses, inter-human relations became in European way (Mardin, 1995).

In the face of such developments that have taken place in sports institutions of other countries with the spread of globalization in the world, Ottoman state lawmakers started to look for solutions after the declaration of Constitution II.

Committee of Union and Progress wanted to take some steps in connection with physical education and sports in order to improve social life and integration. In addition to the need for entertainment by the community, these organizations, which are provided by the social integration and dominated by the ultra-nationalistic atmosphere, have also become an intermediary for communicating the political messages of the Committee of Union and Progress by means of physical education and sports both inside and outside the public.

Horse races and training festivals are among the most important of these organizations (horse races and horses, 1915, Rusen Esref, 191). In order to develop equestrianism and horseback riding, as well as to put a horse in the races, a number of projects were put in place by the Union of Craftsmen (Ihsan Abidin 1917, Sipahi Ocağı Mecmuası, 1915). The idea that everyone who made up the nation should know how to fight, and that he should be ready to fight and physically prepare himself, the Union and Progress manifest clearly in the administrators. It is the lawmakers who examine the experiences of Europeans almost a century past them. They have begun to establish physical education and sports institutions, both in education and in the whole population.

The most important step taken towards physical education and sports applications was taken with the related law which was published in 1913. Primary education became compulsory and physical education course was obliged to all schools. As a matter of fact, in the primary education program brought by this law, it was aimed that the health of the Turkish youth with the hygiene, the training and school games

and the school games were aimed [516]. It was put into action to establish paramilitary associations and societies and sports organizations, which started to be established in 1913. This program has often changed because of some political preferences and various impossibilities. At the beginning of the paramilitary structure, the British model was preferred and then the German school was chosen because of being the ally with Germans. (Polat, 1991; Genç Dernekleri Teşkili Hakkında Kanun-ı Muvakkat ve Talimatname, 1914). In 1908, a private school named Terbiye-i Bodeniye Mektebi was founded by sampling the schools from London, Petersburg, New York, and Stockholm. Swords, rapids, boxing, wrestling, marksmanship, Swedish and German gymnastics courses were tried to be taught. Apart from these, the school would also have tennis, golf and football branches. From the age of seven to sixty years of age, people could continue their education. In addition, this school was expected to open a branch for girls up to the age of 12 in the following years. The School was divided into four classes, which would continue: they were enthusiastic, compulsive enthusiasts, voluntary enthusiasts and arbitrarily enthusiastic. However, this school was closed before becoming fully active (Sivaz, 2016). The modern scouting organization that first appeared in England was soon adopted by the Ottoman intellectuals and their authorities. The reason for this was the fact that your scouts were regarded as a suitable tool for the purposes of the Party of Union and Progress, the ruling party of the time (Karaküçük, 1999). Following the abandonment of British type scouting, the same blotting with Germany, which had experience and experience in paramilitary operations, led to the preference of the Ottoman administrators to shift to this direction (Sivaz, 2016). Thus, instead of the Scout puppet, the German type model was taken as an example, and the Power Associations established on May 28, 1914, began to be emphasized [580]. Scouting continued its activities as part of this foundation. In the context of the First World War, which was the target of all Ottoman and even Islamic geography, it was necessary to take into account the Ottoman geography as a whole and politics accordingly, not just Turkishness. The nature of the war environment, the Ottoman Power, and Young Associations were purely military purposes. The aim was to prepare young people and all Ottoman citizens for the coming World War I (Sivaz, 2016). For this reason, after the first meetings made, the names, places, and numbers of the media, official and private schools and other educational institutions, the preparation of the statements specifying the numbers of the teachers and officials there, were requested from the relevant ministries. For similar reasons, along with the Religious affair Authority, National defense authority and National education authority were supported (Ateş, 2012). The establishment of such associations was encouraged for young people outside the school (Prime Ministry Ottoman Archives, File No: 101, Shirt

No: 18). As a result, the Ottoman Power Association has been removed from the Ottoman Youth Association Guidelines on April 22, 1916, and has left its place in this new association. The main reason for the need for the Ottoman Youth Associations is that the previous associations can't be brought to the desired level and they have not spread all over the Ottoman geography (Sivaz, 2016). It can be said that the Young Associations are a step forward of the Ottoman Empire. It is seen that the aim of the establishment of young associations is more militant in relation to military service, of those who are given training and education. For example, the Power Associations could also be established without being bound to the Harbiye Supervision, all of the Young Associations would be attached to this censure. There was no obligation of the young people raised in the Ottoman Power Associations to enter the military. These were to be taken to the military if they wanted. However, it was obligatory to join the army for the one who left the Ottoman Youth Associations. Similarly, while the target mass of the Ottoman Power Associations was generally school-based, the Ottoman Youth Association was established to educate the entire mass of soldiers, not just the students. It was imperative that these new associations be established with the all-male population in appropriate conditions. Therefore, just as in the Power Associations, not only Muslim youth but also non-Muslims had to enter this organization. Every Ottoman youth was obliged to enter and participate in these associations. The fact that physical education was given to schools all over the country in this way and the spread of Swedish gyms nationwide naturally brings with it the need for teachers. In 1914 Selim Sirri Tarcan Bey opened the Teacher Training School in order to close the gap. Thus, it was aimed to educate Turkish teachers who were specialized in body training (Sivaz, 2016).

One of the incomplete initiatives due to World War I was the "School of Physical Education" which was attempted in 1914. Unlike the attempt in 1908, this school, which was to be established by the state, would be attached to Darülmualim School (Mahmud Cevad, 1920). The construction of the School of Medicine in Vefa, which began in 1915, was closed due to occupation by the military. Since the occupation ended in February 1915, some steps were taken to complete the construction. In this regard, Inspector Mr. Selim Sirri had in particular provided the necessary reports to the relevant authorities. As a result, a letter was written to the director of Darulmuallim School from the Ministry of Education, on March 15, 1916, to keep this school under protection. In 1914, when World War I began, physical education in schools was completely converted to military quality (Sivaz, 2016).

The fact that the Ottoman society lagged behind this understanding in the face of the national defense understanding and the individuals being raised for it in Europe

was taken seriously by the rulers of the state and the communication tools such as newspapers and magazines were utilized to guide the society to this understanding. In particular, the pity picture of the Balkan wars, in contrast to the developments in Europe, fully embraced the idea of eliminating the body weakness of the Turkish race and making it ready for the defense of the homeland (Beşikçi, 2010). Because of the reasons mentioned above, lawmakers in the period are trying to find the truth about paramilitary associations both inexperienced and trial-and-error. In addition, it was thought that it would be correct for the Association of National Defense, which was founded as a paramilitary and charity association, to continue its activities as a charity, and a new association was established for the execution of paramilitary activities. The Turkish Power Society, as its name implies, was established in Istanbul as a nationalist and paramilitary body regimen and health organization (Turkish Gücü, 1911). These activities had to be implemented in order for the Ottoman state and Turkish presence to continue. Legislators who have always been aware of this idea have begun to apply Turkish youth through associations and school programs by militarizing physical education and sports activities after and during the Balkan Wars. Thus, it was directed to paramilitary and gymnastics activities known to have developed disciplined and patriotic virtues, such as that in Europe (Leonard, 1971; Selim Sirgi, 1926) the associations established and supported by the Union and Progress Party used the young people of Turkish society to mobilize for physical exercise and military training.

Minorities within the Ottoman state and representatives of the states with commerce relations were granted the right to form associations and clubs with the declaration of the Constitutional Monarchy. Minorities and representatives of the western countries that have obtained this opportunity have started to establish associations and sports clubs in various cities of the Ottoman state. II. After the declaration of the Constitution, the Ottoman citizens had the right to establish associations and sports clubs. The first football league was established, and the sports competitions under the name of Istanbul League and Friday League started to be done regularly. During this period, the Ottoman state participated in the Olympics by establishing the National Olympic Committee. During this period, three joint-stock companies, which produce sports service by private enterprise, were also established.

4. Results

During the first globalization process, the Ottoman state conquered Istanbul and became an empire. During the establishment phase of the state, the sports schools had three important functions. The first one was to meet the sports needs of the people, the

second was economic and the third was the military purpose. The Ottoman state decision-makers were setting up sports schools in the rural areas where they would settle. Later on, settlement began around these sports schools and over time, they were getting the city. Another purpose was to establish sports schools on the trade routes, thus securing the trade routes, also called the Silk Road. But with the westerners discovering the sea route, the development of the Silk Road has stopped, and over time, the prey has decreased. This development has gradually reduced the importance of sports schools. This change in trade routes has also adversely affected both the cities on the old trade route and the development of sports schools.

In the second globalization process, the physical education and sports policies implemented in the last period of the Ottoman state seem to affect the Republican Period which is the next stage of the Constitution in many respects. Efforts for the re-establishment of the Young Associations in the first years of the Republic are an indication of this. In the following years, especially in the II, before World War II, steps taken in the field of physical education remind the Union and Progress Party of what happened after the Balkan Wars. In this respect, experience, experience, and experience related to physical education and spore were seen during the Republican Period. The right to establish associations and clubs together with the representatives of the Constitutional Monarchy is given to the representatives of the minorities within the Ottoman State and to the commerce-related states. Minorities and representatives of the western countries that have obtained this opportunity have started to establish associations and sports clubs in various cities of the Ottoman state. After the declaration of the Constitution II, the Ottoman citizens had the right to establish associations and sports clubs. The first soccer league was established and sports competitions under the name of Istanbul League and Friday League started to be organized regularly. During this period, the Ottoman state participated in the Olympics by establishing the National Olympic Committee. It is understood that after the Second Constitutional Monarchy, the Unionist politicians were transformed in the direction of national capital with special efforts (Kazgan et al., 1999). The firms established by this turnover are predominantly foreign capital or foreign companies and minority companies jointly established, while the companies established after 1908, especially after the First World War (1914-18) mostly belong to Muslim-Turkish elements (Kepoglu, 2017). During this period, three joint-stock companies which produce sports service by private enterprise were established. Büyükada Yacht Club Anonim Şirketi Osmaniyesi in 1906, Bosphorus Beykoz Park Ottoman incorporated company in 1913 and Beirut Club and Casino Ottoman incorporated company in 1917. Until 1937, Büyükada Yacht Club Holding Company continued its activities until it went bankrupt under the name of Büyükada

Yacht Club Turkish Joint Stock Company. Anadolu Sports Club, established in Mustafa Kemal Atatürk's directive, started its activities under the name of Istanbul branch and continues its activities today (Kepoğlu, 2013).

The sports schools of the Ottoman state's sports institutions were weakened by losing their importance because they were negatively affected by the change of trade routes in the first globalization process and the economic aims of the establishment reasons were deregulated. In the second globalization process; despite the fact that the Ottoman state was in its recent times, it tried to adapt to the socio-economic changes brought about by Globalization. At the end of this effort; education, social life, sports, and sports institutions. Both the sports institutions and the sports labor were transferred to the state of the Republic of Turkey as the continuation of the Ottoman state.

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